

USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN SOLVING GLOBAL FOOD PROBLEMS

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Abstract: The global food problem is one of the oldest problems of humanity. The problem of food shortage and the resulting famine has been considered one of the greatest threats to humanity both in ancient times, in the Middle Ages, and at the present time. Famine can be manifested in two forms. In the first form, famine continues chronically, as a result of which people's health deteriorates, their skin dries up, and the possibility of contracting various diseases increases. This form of starvation is also called "not eating enough food". The second form is the death of millions and tens of millions of people at a certain time in a certain area of the earth's surface due to drought or famine for other reasons. The ever-increasing unrest and other problems related to the human factor cause the issue of food to be on the agenda. Of course, the value of the blessing called food cannot be measured and compared with anything. Therefore, preventing this problem, solving it in time, and determining the future fate of mankind is of great importance.

Key words: Food, small business, entrepreneurship, import, export, foreign economy, investment, innovation

INTRODUCTION

In today's economic and social development of the world community, solving the food problem for every country remains one of the important tasks facing its economy. Because food is considered one of the most important and non-substitutable elements among the elements necessary for life, the occurrence of food shortages due to various reasons leads to many irreversible effects.

can come. The concept adopted by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) is as follows: "all people have access to safe and nutritious food in sufficient quantities to meet their nutritional needs and personal preferences and to lead an active and healthy life." Having the physical, economic and social means to obtain food means ensuring food security". Food consumption directly affects the health of people and nations. Unsatisfactory nutrition destroys human health and causes enormous economic costs to society. Many studies show that poor nutrition is a major obstacle to the food economy of many countries. FAO research on Nutrition and

Economic Growth shows that a one percent increase in protein consumption increases gross domestic product (GDP) by 0.49 percent over the long term. A one percent annual increase in GDP doubles the income of the population in 72 years, and a two percent increase in 36 years. The importance of nutrition in economic food is invaluable. The measures taken to achieve food security in different countries can be divided into the following groups:

- 1) work release support,
- 2) trade,
- 3) consumption and micronutrient substances supply. Development release support measures Green the revolution forward pushes.

As a result, agricultural productivity has increased dramatically, which has helped many countries achieve food security. But some mistakes were made in its implementation. Two directions of trade policy in the analysis of countries:

constraints (including self-sufficiency strategies) and liberalization are demonstrated and explained. We can further analyze consumption support measures and specific experiences in terms of support (targeted to the whole population) and targeted support (targeted to specific disadvantaged categories of the population).

The concept of food security was proposed for the first time in 1974 at the World Food Summit, "the world's supply of basic foodstuffs sufficient to sustain a steady increase in food consumption and to cover fluctuations in production and prices." funds are always available".

In recent years, the concept of food safety has been further expanded to take into account the safety and nutritional value of food products, as well as personal preferences. In 1996, the World Food Security Summit defined the following as a condition of food security:

That all people have physical and economic access to sufficient safe and nutritious food to meet their nutritional needs and personal preferences and to lead active and healthy lives. In 2001, in addition to physical and economic opportunity, the concept of social opportunity was added to the concept of food security. The current definition of FAO reflects this additional aspect as follows. Food security means that all people have the physical, economic, and social capacity to have access to sufficient amounts of safe and nutritious food, according to their nutritional needs and personal preferences, to support an active and healthy life. means mined.

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ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to FAO experts, the situation in terms of food security is determined by food security indicators, supply stability, availability and health. They are defined in detail below.

Stability: a population, family or individual must always have access to food so that the food supply is not interrupted. They should not be cut off from food due to unexpected events (economic) or cyclical events (climatic food shortages).

Food availability: supply of food products of the required quality through domestic production or importation (including food aid) in the required quantity. The most commonly used measure of food availability is per capita daily energy expenditure (DEE), measured in calories. According to FAO methods, the KES indicator is calculated according to the type of food consumption based on the food balance. FAO, using data on the different sources of food supply (production, savings, trade) and the different uses (or consumption) of products (forage, seed, industrial use, waste) of specific commodities, calculates food balances.

Access to food: the physical, economic, and social capacity to access the necessary resources to obtain the nutrients necessary for a nutritious diet. The physical supply of food implies that food products are available on the market in the quantity and choice required by consumers, and that there is an infrastructure for providing the population with food products. Economic opportunity means that all social strata of the population can afford to buy enough food. In other words, economic opportunity means that households have enough income to buy food and the country has enough foreign currency to import food. Social opportunity means that the entire population, regardless of culture or religion, is provided with food fairly.

The volume of imports recorded in the months of 2022 increased by 23.8% compared to the corresponding period of 2021. In this case, the import volume of products is 15,434.8 mln. US dollars and the volume of services is 1,395.7 mln. amounted to US dollars.

Use is to reach a state where all physiological needs are met by consuming food through proper nutrition, clean water, sanitation and hygiene. problem would have been prevented to a great extent. For this purpose, the UN's International Food and Agriculture Organization, FAO, the World Bank and a number of other international organizations are cooperating with the countries of the world community. The causes, current situation and negative aspects of global food problems. one of the problems is the problem of food shortage. This problem has developed differently in different regions. If we look at the origin of the problem, we can see that it is different.

In 2022, food products were imported from 105 countries (and from 104 countries in 2021). Countries with a high share of food imports to the Republic of Uzbekistan: Kazakhstan (37.0%), Russian Federation (24.6%), Brazil (13.8%), Belarus (4.3%) and Pakistan (2.7 %).

Countries with a high share of food imports, thousand. US dollars

The name of the countries	2021	2022
Kazakhstan	499361.0	698 978.8
Russia	377,903.1,	464,001.5
Brazil	176,373.6	260,413.6
Belarus	49,523.8	80,515.6
Pakistan	13,666.7	51,766.3

Turkey	23,273.2	29,253.7
Ecuador	14,184.7	28,889.9
China	22,708.8	27,132.8
Iran	16,359.4	19,705.7
Malaysia	22,669.0	19,144.6
Ukraine	31,313.2	15,990.7
Switzerland	6,784.0	14,952.9
Poland	10,031.4	14,507.4
France	11,261.7	14,033.9
India	6,265.7	13,342.0
Other countries	105 931.4	134 172.6

One of the main reasons for the emergence of the problem is the lack of one of the indicators discussed above, which leads to a low level of food security or lack of food. Food insecurity is a situation in which the population cannot obtain enough safe and nutritious food necessary for normal growth, development and an active lifestyle. Food shortages or low food security levels lead to poor nutrition among the population, which in turn has serious consequences for individuals, families, and the nation as a whole. Inadequate consumption of protein and energy and lack of vital nutrients, especially iodine, vitamin A and iron, have negative consequences for the health of children and adults. According to the FAO, iron deficiency increases the risk of maternal mortality by twenty times. Children's anemia leads to a slowdown in physical, mental and psychomotor development and a weakening of protection against infectious diseases. TTA leads to deterioration of the health of adults and a decrease in labor productivity. The economic and material consequences of poor nutrition are severe. Shortened life or disability due to poor nutrition leads to loss of life productivity in developing countries. The annual productivity index for a child born in Nigeria in 1994 is \$280. As a result of insufficient nutrition, the child may become disabled and partially or completely lose productivity. Introduction 1. Consequences of malnutrition in Nigeria.

In this case, the DALY (disability adjusted life expectancy) index can be calculated as follows: $1.4,855,000 \times 36\% = 1,747,800$ malnourished children. 2.DALY

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= \$280 X 1,747,800 = \$489,384,000 Total number of babies born in Nigeria in 1994 number was 4,855,000. In 1994, the share of undernourished children under 5 years old was 36%. $4,855,000 \times 36\% = 1,747,800$ children were not provided with enough food. DALY = \$280 X 1,747,800 = \$489,384,000 shows that Nigeria can lose \$4,893,840,000 annually due to child malnutrition.

According to FAO estimates, annual losses due to insufficient nutrition are 30 billion. equal to a dollar. According to Jean-Louis Arcand, between the 1960s and 1990s, malnutrition and famine in sub-Saharan Africa resulted in a 0.5-1.5% decrease in GDP per capita each year. Loss of labor productivity due to famine (the direct impact of food on economic growth) accounts for half of this loss. The rest is the result of life shortening due to lack of food. It should be noted that even a one percent decrease in growth has a significant impact on the national economy and the well-being of the population.

The role and activity of the UN Food and Agriculture Organization in the regulation of global food problems is one of the important tasks facing not only one country but the entire international community. In the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, a number of works and international agreements on the solution of this issue were carried out between several countries in the context of ensuring food safety. The first of these and the most important in terms of scale is the conference dedicated to international food problems in Rome in May-June 1905, initiated by the American scientist and agricultural specialist David Lubin. At this conference, an agreement was reached on the establishment of the International Food Institute. Later, on the basis of this organization, on October 16, 1945, at an international meeting in Quebec City, Canada, the international organization FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) was established. aims to help countries of the world in ensuring poverty and food security.

The main task of this organization was determined as follows:

- providing assistance to developed and developing countries in the fight against hunger,
- ensuring food safety, supporting agricultural food supply;
- ensuring the productivity of agriculture, forestry, marine products;
- prevention of poverty in rural areas, social protection of the poor population;
- prevention of hunger and poverty in rural areas;

- to assist countries in creating a safe and efficient food system,
- to help countries preserve and restore food and agricultural systems during man-made and natural disasters.

Today, FAO works in cooperation with a number of other international organizations in fulfilling the tasks it has set for itself. Among them are the World Bank, the World Health Organization, the Asian Development Bank and other prestigious international organizations. Together with these organizations, assistance is provided to developing countries with food problems through a number of international programs.

Achieving food security in many countries of the world depends on the implementation of strategies and programs in agriculture and trade. They can be divided into the following groups:

- Production support policy;
- Trade policy;
- Consumer support strategies;

It should be noted that such programs were not mutually exclusive and were implemented simultaneously in many countries. They can be analyzed below:

In the second half of the 20th century, a sudden increase in crop yields, known as the Green Revolution, greatly increased food production. According to FAO data, between 1980 and 2000, the yield of wheat increased by 208 percent, and the yield of rice, corn, and potatoes increased by 109, 157, and 78 percent, respectively³. The sharp increase in crop productivity was mainly due to scientific and technical progress, including high-yielding varieties of crops, wider use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, as well as irrigation and mechanization. These technologies are due to the intensive development of agriculture with a slight expansion of the cultivated area. For example, in the 1960s, a high-yielding rice variety was introduced. By 1989, the area of rice cultivation increased by only 13%, but the amount of the crop increased from 240 million to 483 million. At the same time, the rate of use of mineral fertilizers increased from 17 kg to 110 kg per hectare.

Trade policy Food trade policy in different countries is carried out in the direction of restricting trade and liberalizing trade. Trade restrictions are one of the actively used methods in this regard. Despite the growth in international food trade, 90 percent of food products are consumed in the country's domestic markets. Such a high percentage

is due to restrictions imposed by many countries on food imports to achieve food security. This is usually done through licensing, high tariffs and fees to protect national producers and ensure self-sufficiency in food. Food self-sufficiency programs are mainly aimed at supporting the cultivation of the most essential crops, including wheat, rice and other cereal crops. Consumption Support Policy. The purpose of consumer support programs is to provide the economic opportunity for the entire population or a part of it to have certain food products.

Targeted food assistance programs are aimed at ensuring food security for special groups of the population. For example, many countries have a free or reduced-price school meal program. These programs serve to improve children's mental and physical development, strengthen their ability to read and sleep, and increase labor productivity in the country in the future. Targeted programs can also target populations such as pregnant women, women with infants, and pre-school children.

The scale of the food problem in developing countries, its causes and the factors affecting it. The 1998 Human Development Report prepared by the United Nations Development Program provides the following information: World consumption level from 1.5 trillion US dollars in 1950 to 1990 increased to 4 trillion US dollars. In 25 years from 1950 to 1975, consumption tripled to 12 trillion US dollars. From 1975 to 1998, in 23 years, it doubled again to -24 trillion US dollars.

Over the past 25 years, per capita consumption in developed countries has increased steadily (about 2.3% per year), particularly high in East Asia (6.1%) and growing in South Asia (2, 0%) was observed. Nevertheless, developing countries lag far behind the level of developed countries, where the growth of per capita consumption is very slow or almost unchanged.

The average family in Africa consumes 25% less than it did 25 years ago. The poorest 20% of the world's population is excluded from the very rapid increase in consumption. More than 1 billion people cannot meet their basic consumer needs.

The Director of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations noted the following in his statement dedicated to the World Food Day in 2000: Hunger and poverty cannot be accepted mentally, so it is necessary to put an end to these situations. Starvation and not eating enough all the time shortens human life. Lack of physical or financial access to safe, nutritious and healthy food has negative consequences for peoples and nations. This module focuses on the concept of "food

security" and ways to achieve it. New ideas about the growth of the population have shown the need to reconsider the old traditional views about "overpopulation". Due to the lack of critical evaluations, views of population growth have given rise to concepts of "worldwide famine" and "millions of hungry people". However, it is necessary to take into account that this is not always true, but these perceptions can be the tragic consequences of drought, repression or war. The connection between famine and population is not a simple matter. For example, the Netherlands and Singapore are among the most densely populated countries in the world, but very few people would say that these countries are overpopulated. Food safety in Uzbekistan and ways to ensure it.

Achieving sustainable long-term food security is an important task interdependent with the macroeconomic, political and social success of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is difficult to achieve it without solving major macroeconomic and agricultural problems. In order to achieve food security, it is necessary to develop and implement a comprehensive institutional policy on agriculture, improving population welfare, continuous and sustainable economic growth, and reducing the level of poverty. The experience of many countries shows that the main condition and factor for reducing poverty is economic growth. It increases the standard of living and improves the consumption of food products. Liberalization and increasing international trade volumes will improve food diversity and economic availability. FAO's research on trade and food security identifies the direct link between international trade, economic growth and food security. Free international trade in food products eliminates imbalances in agriculture and helps to optimize production. International trade helps the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan to identify its relative advantages and use them more effectively. Import of food products allows to increase the level of supply of food products in the domestic market, reduce prices and create a competitive environment for local producers and, as a result, forces them to increase their efficiency. Exporting food products allows local producers to compete in foreign markets while also forcing them to reduce costs and work more efficiently. Finally, international trade stimulates economic growth and improves living standards, which in turn increases food security, the economic popularity and consumption of food products. The basis of food security is domestic production. sufficient amount of food of the required quality supplied by export or import. Food supply at the national level is usually expressed in the food

balance. The volume of food production, taking into account their export and import, can serve as an indicator of the country's overall food supply. Food trade.

Trade makes it possible to use the country's relative advantages in agricultural production. Food imports can increase the level of food supply in the domestic market and create conditions for competition with local producers. The export of food products allows local producers to compete in foreign markets. Internal and external international competition creates incentives for increased efficiency.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, we can say that Uzbekistan can completely cover its food needs through its own potential. is the result of reforms.

The world population continues to grow, according to the UN, by 2050, the population of our planet will reach nine billion. Therefore, it can be observed that the problem of food supply will become more urgent. It should be noted that the majority of people suffering from the problem of food shortage and poverty in the world, 65 percent to be precise, are not in less developed countries, but in developing countries. they live Such people make up about 2 billion of the world's population. 1.4 billion of them live in developing countries, and 600 million live in poor countries.

According to Andy Sumner, a professor at the Institute for Development Studies at Success University, average incomes have risen significantly in many countries over the past decade. But despite the predictions, the reduction of poverty was observed to a small extent. One of the goals of the UN Millennium Development Program is to drastically reduce poverty and hunger by 2030. Although the efforts in this direction are very fruitful, the financial and economic crisis that has arisen in recent years has aggravated the situation. The number of people living on one dollar a day is not decreasing even in countries whose economy is growing by five to six percent per year. This means that the number of people who become victims of the problem of food shortage and poverty is increasing.

In recent years, various factors, including the weather, have put the world's main agricultural regions in a difficult situation. In the process of in-depth study and analysis of this problem, the following suggestions can be implemented using the above conclusions:

Increasing the importance of international organizations to improve the existing agricultural structure and standard of living in developing countries;

conducting scientific research within the framework of promotion of rational nutrition and healthy lifestyle;

increase the scope of use of livestock and fishery resources, which are a source of food in addition to agriculture;

it is necessary to expand the volume of intensively used land at the expense of new land, to increase the biological productivity of existing land.

If the above suggestions are put into practice, the food problem would be prevented to some extent. For this, it is necessary to increase the biological productivity of the existing lands. Biotechnology, the use of new, high-yielding varieties of plants and new methods of soil cultivation, mechanization, chemicalization, and further development of land reclamation are important in the implementation of this path.

Therefore, reforming the agricultural sector, providing it with modern, harmless technologies is one of the most urgent tasks facing all countries. At a time when such complex processes are going on in the world, the fact that prices are not allowed to increase sharply in our country, grain threshing is increasing every year, is another sign that human beings are valued in our republic, and human interests are the highest value.

The most important thing is that during the past short period of independence, our Motherland gained grain independence, not only fully satisfying the needs of our thirty-five million people, but also becoming one of the countries that export grain abroad, and our people A good standard of living, the fact that our markets are full of products, strengthens our confidence in our future.

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